

ON THE ROLE OF CONCEPTS AND KNOWLEDGE STRUCTURE IN COGNITIVE SEMANTICS

Amirova Zohida Oripovna

teacher of Karshi state university

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An approach to the study of a concept as a structure of knowledge considers knowledge in the form of a substance that man forms in the form of concepts such as “concept is always knowledge embedded in frames” (Telia 1996: 96). The creator of frame theory, Marvin Minsky (Minsky 1974), understands frame as data structure - data-structure: this theory has been developed in cybernetics alongside research on artificial intelligence and takes on an artificial character as a frame data presentation structure (Shenk 1994). Current research on the concept does not include articles in dictionaries. In doing so, the researcher is based on the rule that the concept will be present (will be presented) in the lexical structure of the language, whether explicitly or unknowingly. However, the example in English shows that the unity of language does not mean the unity of concepts.

In our opinion, it is inappropriate to consider the relationship between the knowledge of the world and the “simple” landscape of the world, which is more relevant to the scientific landscape of the world than to the linguistic landscape of the world. : we see the world as expressed in its language) (Postovalova 1998; Grigoreva 2003; Serebrennikov 1988). At the same time, some researchers have developed a simple-language view of the world (Apresyan 2001), a linguistic, practical view of the world that is contrasted with the scientific view of the universe (Holland 1984; Lakoff, Ryabtseva 2005). On the other hand, the scientific knowledge that operates because of the scientific tradition and the texts created within this tradition also belongs to society in some sense, that is, scientific knowledge goes beyond the boundaries of the field of knowledge in which science operates and becomes public property through scientific and popular genre texts. For example, the perception of the Earth as a planet by someone who now lives in Russia and has at least a high school education is radically different from, say, the perception of the Earth in the twelfth century: the modern citizen assumes that the Earth is flat and the Sun revolves around it difficult to reach. But in a normal life situation, we say, “the sun is setting” and “the sun is rising.” At the same time, we are well aware of the situation that language “draws” or presents to us, how far the linguistic landscape of the world is actually in the scientific landscape of the universe (Kornilov 2003; Kolshansky 1990; Yakimovich 2004). Most scholars acknowledge that a concept is undoubtedly a “separate sign” (Alefirenko 2005),

i.e., that it is related to a vague essence, i.e., a resonant or written word: should be expressed as a question of how much information quantum can be extracted from the general flow of information by means of symbols "(Kubryakova 1992: 23). It is difficult to define a conceptual connection with a sign, because the action of a concept (concept) depends on the action of society, and therefore language, and, consequently, the sign of a concept or concept: without a sign - there is no concept as a structure of mind the connection of language is inseparable, and thought constantly senses the influence of language (Avoyan 1985). However, some scholars have stuck to the idea that "not all concepts can be objectified through language" (Grishchuk 1998; Popova, Sternin, Charikov 1998: Popova, Sternin 2001).

It is not an easy task to clearly articulate the so-called "cognitive product" of the concept expressed in language. In this sense, the concept of TRAVEL is a good example (Bobrova 2005). A decision regarding the naming of a concept is difficult because a whole series of words that serve as a concept symbol in English: journey, trip, voyage, expedition, ride, drive? flight, passage, excursion, crossing, tour, trek, outing, pilgrimage, jaunt are available, in Russian: (puteshestvie) the word travel can be a symbol of such a concept. Will each of these words be a sign of a separate concept of 'its own' or the same concept? Also some concepts. V. I. Speaking of concepts that do not rotate directly in the language, Karasik is rightly represented by phrases, such as the smell of bread now coming out of the oven (Karasik 1996). If the agap is that all of these are different concepts, then each of them must have its own components: if not, and they are all components of a single complex concept, then what sign serves as the name of this complex concept? Finally, the problem of the presence / absence of certain concepts in different languages is cross-referenced: in the languages of different peoples there are often words that are not similar in other languages. For example, in the Aztec language of eastern Central America, there is no separate word for the side of the human body - only the thorax and abdomen are distinguished. Naturally, the Aztecs also do not have a concept that corresponds to the word bikin (Wierzbicka 1988). The concept is provided by a complex prototypical representation of interactions at the level of the nervous system of the individual: "the interaction of the studied organism with the environment leads to the formation of simple representations. As the number of interactions with homogeneous components in the environment increases, the representation of such interactions becomes more complicated ...

As the experience of interaction with the environment increases, simple prototypical representations begin to function only as part of the composition of complex prototypical representations. ... in which case it also leads to the activation of the whole complex representation. The same thing could have happened if the organism had interacted with the obvious essence that corresponds to this representation ... When we hear the word "smoke," we can imagine and smell the smoke in front of our eyes, just as we know it is the smell of smoke. »(Kravchenko 2001: 2005). The close continuous connection between the component of the environment (smell of smoke, its color, opacity) and the sign (a word that is an integral part of the environment like smoke) is ensured due to the state of neuronal activity. But does the total complex representation of reciprocal actions become more active in the communication process? It is unthinkable that in the process of a cardiologist's communication with a client suffering from heart disease, the word heart is interpreted in a figurative sense: heart or central part (the use of the word heart in the sense of central area or most important part is very specific to English). In this case, the client is primarily concerned about the heart as a member of the human body and its disease. This suggests that when interacting with a character, not all of the representation in the communication process is activated, but only a part of it, or that a character is an integral part of several complex representations.

It is difficult to answer within the framework of existing approaches based not only on linguistics, but also on the data of other disciplines, and some of the questions that cannot be answered at all are: where the concepts apply, how and at what expense the connections between them are ensured. What is "polyapellation" or "multiple ways of accessing a concept" (Karasik, Slisshkin 2001: Slisshkin 2005: 38), how the mind works with concepts (Boldirev 2000: 23), why different words are different in the minds of different people belonging to the same culture means concepts (Frumkina 1992: 97) and others - like many other questions, these questions remain unanswered.

So, if a concept is a logically artificial situation, an artificial construct, then for what purpose is it created, modeled? Apparently, a concept, like many other concepts in cognitive science (frame, script, etc.), can also be a tool to help identify and interpret general mechanisms that underlie language interpretation alone. There is no compelling reason to say that the connection between the representation of interactions and the sign is only one-sided, i.e., the representation can function as an exponent and vice versa: it depends on what we base it on. But neither mathematicians nor physicists are serious about the

existence of essences such as vectors, straight lines, spheres, logarithms, derivatives or integrals, their complex structure, connections and interactions.

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